

The Envisioning Report for Empowering Universities

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The fourth Envisioning Report for Empowering Universities in the uptake of new modes of teaching and learning

We herewith present to you the fourth edition of the EMPOWER Envisioning report on innovating higher education. The report is set up by the expert pools of the EMPOWER programme established by EADTU to cover the latest trends and developments in new modes of teaching. New modes of teaching and learning create new opportunities for enhancing the quality of the learning experience in on campus programmes, reaching out to new target groups off campus and offering freely accessible courses nationally or worldwide through the internet. They enhance the quality, visibility and reputation of the institution. The EMPOWER expert pools are working in all relevant areas for the development of new modes of teaching and learning. The EMPOWER website, covering 12 expert pools, can be found [here](#).

The actual implementation of innovative methods in teaching and learning requires institutional strategies and frameworks. A strong motivation of a professional teaching staff and continuous commitment from the top management of a higher education institution is needed to make this a success. With the EMPOWER Envisioning report we want to inspire fellow experts in innovating education by examples from practice. In this 4th issue of 2020 we cover new initiatives related to Open Educational Resources and Open Practices; Learning Analytics and Artificial Intelligence; Continuing Education and Curriculum and Course Design.

The Envisioning report is a selection of good practices and studies done by the experts connected to EADTU's EMPOWER programme. EMPOWER is further supporting individual universities by on site expert seminars with free independent advice, onsite and online seminars, guidance for university leaders, expert panels for targeted reviews and, support for whole of institution initiatives. Further, EMPOWER hosts the Empower Online Learning Leadership Academy (EOLLA) on new and emerging models of teaching and learning.

We certainly believe also this edition of the year 2020 is an inspiration for many to further innovate education and start cooperation and sharing of expertise with fellow innovators.

George Ubachs
Managing Director EADTU

Bridging the Digital Divide Through ODL

Innovative impact

As a phenomenon of the digital age, digital divide has begun to show its influence more clearly in societies. Especially in these Corona Days this division is expected to continue to increase with the proliferation of digital technologies.

ODL as an open community movement in education has an invisible effect to bridge the digital divide in society by integrating current technologies in learning. In this paper, the potential of ODL for bridging the digital divide investigated based on studies from different countries.

Introduction

In the majority of research on digital division, technological opportunities (physical access to computers, networks and other technologies) take the first place, followed by demographic characteristics (income, education, age, gender and ethnicity).

OECD has identified communication infrastructures, computer availability, internet access, accessibility via TV and mobile phones as indicators of the digital divide. OECD also reported that household income and education levels are important determinants. In this context, the size and type of the household, age, gender, race, language, and settlements are also among the indicators of the digital divide. In measuring digital division, the distribution of various indicators to the demographic structure of individuals forming the society is generally used with ICT.

Open and distance learning, by its nature, should utilize the current technology, follow changing sociological structures and offer appropriate opportunities accordingly. These missions of ODL empower to bridge the digital divide in society.

Various efforts have been developed to measure digital division, which is important for all countries and communities, especially during the Coronavirus outbreak. Covid-19 pandemic forced society to use digital technologies not only for learning but also for their works, shopping, social activities etc. In other words, digital technologies are the main communications way of our daily life today. This paper investigated the national efforts and studies from different countries.

ODL for Digital Divide

In the 21st century, when information technologies began to be used extensively, the digital divide started to show its effect more clearly in societies. Because in the 21st-century society of the individual, digital technologies have started to take an indispensable role in communication, transportation, business, education and even access to public services. Especially for demographic differences like disadvantaged groups, geographical difficulties, natural limitations such as pandemic outbreaks. The digital divide that occurs between different segments and groups of society can significantly affect the social life of these segments and groups. Similar situations are highlighted in countries with the digital divide.

It is thought that it can benefit from open and distance learning with its mass feature and technology intensive application tools in dealing with digital division, which is seen as one of the important problems of the digital period. Researches also show that ODL reduces digital division.

The spread of open and distance learning in the world is not limited to only

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higher education. Although higher education has a leading role in this area, open and distance learning services are actively used in elementary and secondary schools. Additionally, ODL has been used in the education given to handicapped individuals and in foreign language teaching.

Coronavirus COVID-19 pandemic was declared by World Health Organization on 11th March, 2020. Many countries in the world are trying to create curfews, social distances, and conditions for staying at home. Quarantine, which is applied all over the world, has also brought education to homes. Fortunately, we have strong ODL experiences and infrastructure supported by computer and internet technology. Anyone with computer and internet technology can have the opportunity to receive a world-class education. This situation shows that open and distance education is quite important for equal opportunity, democracy and citizenship in this information age.

Global Cases

Chen & Wellman (2004) states that the spread of the Internet and the accompanying digital division consist of national and international socioeconomic, technological and linguistic differences. With the spread of the Internet, the digital gap between North America and other developed countries is narrowing, but is still largely present.

Mariscal (2005) investigated the cause of digital division in a developing country such as Mexico and provided evidence that digital division did not decrease with the increase of telecommunication networks.

In the study conducted by Fuchs and Horak (2008), it was concluded that although the number of internet and mobile technology users increased in Ghana and South African countries, poverty, cultural and social polarization, income distribution inequalities and other ethnic problems could not prevent digital division. For Africa, digital division has been seen as a problem arising from the structural inequalities of the global network society, characterized by global, social and ethnic discrimination. Radojičić (2011) designed a model to measure 5 types of digital division (age, gender, region, educational level and income level) and digital division in the population area. This model was applied in Serbia by calculating five sub-indexes and compound digital polarization index for the years 2009-2010. According to the results of the research, the difference in the use of information technologies is increasing between the young and old population, and efforts to reduce digital division continue, although it is still very slow.

In their study, Cruz-Jesus, Oliveira and Bacao (2012) conducted to analyze the digital division within the European Union-27 between 2008 and 2010, five digital profiles were identified among the 27 member states. These digital differences have been associated with economic asymmetries between countries, and it has been suggested that the year of entry into the European Union also affected the divisions. On the other hand, contrary to the results of some previous studies, it has been concluded that the school attendance of the population does not have a significant importance in digital division.

Büchi, Just and Latzer (2015) conducted surveys on internet use and developed comparative research on second-level digital division by modeling Internet use inequalities for five countries (New Zealand, Sweden, the United States, Switzerland, the UK) that have reduced access difficulties. It was concluded that sociodemographic alone constitutes half of the variance in these five countries and that age is the strongest predictor.

Conclusion

The results of the studies carried out in different geographies, different continents and countries in different socio-economic levels are given in this study. The results show that digital division is related to socio-cultural characteristics as well as technology. As a socio-cultural activity, the technology intensive structure of distance education also encourages the individual to use technology more effectively.

During the Covid-19 pandemic, universities, high schools, primary schools, private schools and even kindergartens had to be closed. Millions of students had to study in their homes. In these processes, governments and related ministries rushed to discuss how to train so many students at home. It was noteworthy that governments, like most of the society, got to know the developed ODL area. When it was seen that a training that surpasses traditional education with computer and internet supported ODL is possible, this surprise has increased even more.

Children, young people and adults who continue their education at home now experience ODL. For this, they discover computers, smartphones, smart televisions, live lesson applications, LMS systems and educational content, especially internet technologies. This intense technology demand and need also contributes to the reduction of digital division in society through education.

Contributing institutions

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Hellenic Open University (HOU) | Greece
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